

LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF SUCCESSION PLANNING AND MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AMONG EDUCATIONAL LEADERS AT GULF COLLEGE, OMAN

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Abstract:

The study aimed to determine the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of educational managers at Gulf College, Oman. Specifically, it sought to establish the significant relationship of the respondents' personal profiles and their level of awareness in succession planning and management practices. This study employed the descriptive-evaluative method. The respondents were the educational leaders (deputy deans, head of faculty, program leaders, coordinators and centre managers, lecturers). Statistical procedures were used to analyse the quantitative data such as Frequency and Percentage Distributions and Weighted mean and Computed r . The results show that in terms of talent training and development and process evaluation as against the respondents' profile, the result showed that only the respondents' age has a significant relationship in terms of succession planning and management practices. The levels of awareness of the respondents as regards to succession planning and management practices in terms of communicate expectations and organization assessment and alignment must be strengthened, since they have a verbal interpretation of aware. Likewise, the level of awareness of the respondents as regards to succession planning and management practices in terms of talent training and development as well as process evaluation have marked less aware, this implies that although educational leaders have some knowledge in succession planning and management practices, their involvement is limited. Hence, implementation is not actualized. In order to keep abreast with the challenging academic set ups educational leaders, particularly the top and middle managers should provide an open avenue in succession planning and practices specifically in communicate expectations, organization and assessment, talent and training development programs, and process evaluation. An apprenticeship programs must be provided for incoming educational leaders or managers.

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I. The Problem and its Background

1. Introduction

The need for academic stability of every Higher Education Institutions lies on how educational leaders look into future necessities of academic challenges. One of the challenges is the ability to identify and keep the right people in the right positions. Thus, this would sustain academic growth of every institution. Gonzalez (2010) observed in her paper that although academic is becoming more like a business, it has not borrowed one of the best attributes of business culture: its tradition of developing leadership through succession planning. Academe is also open for changes like transition of administration, restructuring and downsizing- these are all part of the reality. Having this anticipation, academic organizations develop their long and short term plans based on present situation as well as for future events. Taking HEI as no different from a complex business organization, successful succession planning and leadership management models or strategies in the corporate can be adapted for effective implementation (Shamsuddin, 2012).

Seemingly, Gonzalez (2010) as cited by Shamsuddin (2012) mentioned that highly successful organizations are generally not without a critical mass of advocates with a passionate espousal of succession planning as vital to the very survival and sustainability of the organization. Likewise, it helps develop the potentiality of the staff and support them in their respective chosen field to ensure that the organization has pools of talent for key spots. Employees play a role in the process by identifying their career interests, having an opportunity to be assessed for key roles, and developing their learning plans.

Higher learning institutions, considered as academic organizations must hold true to the implementation of succession planning and practices, since they are, there is an apparent distinction between and among its members. Gonzalez (2010) makes a distinction between two levels of academic administrators: deans and above are (professional administrators) and department chairs and below are (casual administrators). Since all faculty members engage in managerial activities as directors of academic programs, principal investigators of grants, committee members or chairs. She proposes that the connection between the guild and the corporation be strengthened and become more of a two-way street.

Educational managers in Higher learning institutions in general may oversight the shortage in leadership talent in the coming years; hence, this may result to leadership crisis. The collaborative function of leadership development and succession planning will create a strong academic culture. Succession planning and management

serve as a way to discover who can be trained to be tomorrow's leaders. Conger and Fulmer (2003, 78) have called the combination of the two traditionally separate practices of succession planning and leadership development, succession management. Thus, it provides an organization with a surplus of talent by helping members realize their potential which should not be confused with performance (Gonzalez, 2010).

It is truly essential in every organization to prepare employees for future leadership roles and opportunities. In order to keep abreast with the demands of the present time, academic leaders must provide programs and plans to develop internal successors who will take the lead and remain competitive in the future.

Inadequate research on this topic driven this study which sought to understand if Higher Education Institutions are prepared to meet these challenges and if so, what plans and programs they employ.

1.1 Background of the Study

Academic organization is never apart from corporate organization since both require workforce to sustain the call for innovation and development. Beerel (2009) cited that to remain relevant in this challenging world requires organization to be adaptive, creative and innovative. This means that the mission or underlying purpose of the organization must be made relevant through vision statements that lay out goals and strategies that cohere with the organization's competencies and above all address changing realities. Being in tune with new realities is what makes organizations adaptive and creative.

HEIs may overlook the need for succession planning practices as an answer to the declining number of qualified and potential leaders in the education sector. This is because most school administrators do not provide assessment needs to the faculty and staff prior to the implementation of development programs. Hence, these programs do not necessarily answer the training needs of the faculty and staff. In fact, some training programs are either repetition or duplication of previously administered training or not at all aligned with the responsibilities and functions to be performed by the faculty or staff. Organizational alignment of development programs in accordance with the needs of employees will ensure continuity of service.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

The researcher adopted the framework of Leslie Ann Wright Coward (2012) *Succession Planning and Management Process Relationship Framework*. Coward developed a conceptual framework as a guide for her study. In her framework, she explained the process that links to program themes and reflects the relationship between each component. She further explained that the support and commitment of leadership is viewed as a bottom up and top-down process that is connected to all succession planning and management components. The inner section, succession planning and management components, of this relationship model reflects a process that connects the different program components and committed leadership. The four components are: communicate expectations, organizational assessment and alignment, talent training

and development, and process evaluation which can be evaluated independently by assigning these specific tasks.

Figure 1: Succession Planning and Management Process Relationship Framework

Based on Coward Wright succession planning and management framework, the process relationship of the four components such as communicate expectations, organization assessment and alignment, talent training and development and process evaluation are interconnected. Subsequently, when the succession planning and management components are achieved on a high level, it will result to leadership commitment and support. Indeed, leadership competencies and leadership succession must be a journey in the organization to institute leadership commitment in order to have strong and solid leadership continuity.

Wright Coward (2012) presented the succession planning and management components. The first component is *Communicate expectations* that review the actions of the college's leadership. It underscores the importance of the board of trustees to establish policies that guide the college as mentioned by (Groves, 2007). The CEO actively participates in the succession planning and management process, and communicates the importance of developing talent internally.

The second component is *Organization assessment and alignment* this refers to the strategic process that informs the college of the internal development and recruitment needs of the institution (Fulton-Calkins & Milling, 2005; Kesler, 2002; McDonald, 2008). The organizational assessment identifies the number of people

eligible for retirement and positions that may be impacted by a leadership shortage. The organization is able to strategically identify internal positions and competencies needed for the continued growth of the institution. Organization alignment provides direction to developing talent. She highlighted that the integration of succession planning and the strategic goals and unit plans of the college provide a guide to how the organization will succeed at succession planning and management. Moreover, this process ensures that the necessary resources and strategic direction are there for the long-term success of the program.

The third component is *Talent training and development* as such is dependent on the results of the organization assessment and alignment. The organization assessment reveals the training and development needs of employees. Talent training and development ensures that the organization has the qualified talent needed to fill future leadership positions. The institution's leadership may demonstrate support of the training and development of employees by creating mentor and leadership training programs, by utilizing individual employee development plans, and by identifying and/or developing a qualified pool of talent. The development of internal talent validates the importance of employees, ensures optimum utilization of human capital, and increases employee job knowledge and skills (Karaevli & Hall, 2003; Kerr & Jackofsky, 1989; Kim, 2003; Leibman, Bruer, & Maki, 1996; van Amburgh et al., 2010).

The final component is *Process evaluation*. It recognizes that succession planning and management is a fluid program that must be modified to meet the internal needs of the organization. Various authors agreed on the importance of linking succession planning to long-term strategic plans which involves measurement and holds leadership and the organization accountable for the success of the program (Conger & Fulmer, 2003; Conger, 2007; Rothwell, 2010). Process evaluation also provides the leadership and organization information about the operation, strengths, and weaknesses of the succession planning and management program. In addition, it ensures that the program is accomplishing its goals. This framework is a process that links all program themes and reflects the relationship between each component. Although succession practices are independent of each other, this model shows the relationship among the four common components.

The Succession Planning and Management Process Relationship framework of Cowards served as the basis of the theoretical framework of this study. Indeed, this framework would be of varying significance in as much as this study was conducted. The framework presented and used was employed in figuring out its conceptual framework. The succession planning and management practices framework of Leslie Ann Coward Wright would establish a relationship as regards to the profiles of educational leaders.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: Research Paradigm

The conceptual framework in Figure 2 presented the different interacting variables in this study. The boxes represented the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables consist of personal profiles such as age, educational attainment and academic positions. The arrow pointing to the box of the dependent variables consist of the succession planning and management practices such as communicate expectations, organization alignment and assessment, talent training and development and process evaluation. This framework determines to establish the significant relationship of the respondents' profile and succession planning and management practices.

2.3 Statement of the Problem

The main problem of this study is to determine the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of succession planning of Gulf College.

1. What is the profile of the respondents based on the following personal variables?

1.1 Age;

1.2 Educational Attainment;

1.3 Academic Positions.

2. What is the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of the respondents in terms of:

2.1 Communicate Expectations;

2.2 Organization Assessment and Alignment;

2.3 Talent and Training Development;

2.4 Process Evaluation?

3. Is there a significant relationship on the level of succession planning and management practices of the respondents when grouped according to profile?

2.4 Scope and Limitation

The scope of the study was to determine the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of the respondents. The study was limited in determining the succession planning and management practices of educational leaders in Gulf College. The respondents were composed of Deputy Deans, Head of Faculty, Program Leaders, Centre Managers, Coordinators and lecturers.

2.5 Significance of the Study

Excellent and exceptional leaders are assets of any organization, specifically in academic setting. Indeed, leadership is a skill that can facilitate one to unleash the full potential of every employee. However, excellent leaders are diminishing, thus the need for growing own potential leaders within the organization is an urgent call for the present educational leaders.

The findings of this study would be of great importance to the following:

- **Educational institutions.** The result of this study offered relevant ideas and strategies as regards to the integration of succession planning in the strategic plan of the institution.
- **Educational leaders and managers.** Educational leaders and managers are referred to empowered people designated to function as educational leaders, through this study, they can be helped in leading and managing their people. likewise, they can be helped in employing appropriate succession planning strategies in the selection of potential leaders for the continuity of service.
- **Faculty members.** Being the prime successor to hold key positions in the educational institutions. This study may likewise give them opportunities to improve their competencies for possible future leadership roles.
- **Other researchers.** The researcher with great desire to give insight to other researchers who will be interested in this study and will consider this for their future investigation.

II. Review of Related Literature and Studies

This chapter presents various literatures in forms of books, journals and previous studies which are related to this present study. The researcher posed different views on leadership, managerial competencies, and succession planning and management researches from local and foreign authors.

2. On Succession Planning and Management

Higher Educational Institutions are never apart from corporate organizations adhering to the same goal—the quest for innovation and stability. The question on how to remain steadfast amidst the challenges of globalization is a serious call for all educational leaders. To be able to address this need for survival; administrative leaders recognize the task to cope with the expectations imposed by the ever changing needs of the society.

The indispensable leadership issues cannot be taken aside, as the organization moves toward the attainment of goals. Essentially, development programs are needed to measure performance and select people to hold pertinent posts in the administration, for that reason, succession planning is vital to ensure that there will be available talent pools to perform and deliver in the workforce.

The marriage of leadership development and succession planning must be taking place within the organization. The intertwined relation between leadership development and succession planning give direction to organization. Succession management approaches are being used to facilitate effective organizational positioning and development to ensure that within an organization the “right” leaders are available at the “right” time (Rothwell, 2001).

Conger and Fulmer (2003) emphasized that an effective succession management plan requires the identification of key knowledge positions and including those in the succession plan, being transparent with employees about all aspects of the plan, rigorous use of measurements, and the inclusion of some flexibility in the plan so it is easily adjusted to changes in the environment.

Indeed, leadership development programs and succession planning need to be given much attention to attract develop and retain leadership pool that will help maintain long term sustainability and viability.

Fulmer (2005), as cited by Erasmus, said that the larger issue is leadership development, tracking, and developmental opportunities. The real key in succession management is to create a match between organization’s future needs and the aspirations of individuals. The only way to keep talented people is to provide them with growth opportunities that keep them stretching and finding more promising they might find elsewhere. Recruiting and retaining leaders becomes an economic and strategic challenge.

According to Christe (2005) in her study entitled “Learning to Grow our Own: A study of Succession Planning at Douglas College”, succession planning can provide a significant organizational intervention opportunity to respond to the impending loss of leadership personnel. Effective strategic planning for leadership development can position an institution to attract external people and retain current employees with leadership potential. For those who practise informal leadership, opportunities exist for developing competency directed at moving into formal leadership roles. For those currently in formal leadership roles, opportunities for further leadership development can help with upward mobility into executive leadership roles. Succession planning can lead to greater job satisfaction for all employee groups.

While it is true that succession planning served as a way by which organizations evaluate and promote leadership talent., Hughes, Ginnett, and Curphy (2009), On the contrary, mentioned the implication of succession planning in organizations, such as family –owned businesses where family members, often sons and daughters are promoted into critical leadership positions because of their familial relationships with the owner rather than on the basis of their leadership skills. On one hand, in some privately held companies, such as Saudi Aramco, Marriott and Carlson Companies, this process of having successive generations of family members take over multibillion-dollar family businesses has worked quite well. On the other hand, Bill Ford’s takeover of Ford Motor Company several years ago has been nothing short of disastrous (Hughes, Ginnett, and Curphy 2009, 96). They further highlighted the idea that one of

the best practice techniques organizations can use for succession planning is the nine-cell matrix. This nine-cell matrix has two major dimensions. The leadership potential dimension assesses the extent to which candidates are capable of assuming greater responsibility and are likely to be successful if promoted one or two levels up in the organization while the leadership performance dimension assesses the extent to which candidates are achieving results. Organizations use nine-cell matrices to determine possible successors for critical leadership positions, design customized development and retention programs for different cells, and revamp recruiting and selection systems. An article entitled "Succession Planning and Building Your Leadership Pipeline" stressed that an effective succession plan helps identify and groom high potential managers for advancement into key, senior positions, while a leadership pipeline cultivates a pool of quality leaders with diverse management expertise, and provides them with opportunities for professional growth. This strengthens institutional department from within through increased departmental performance, employee satisfaction and retention, as well as creating an infrastructure for leadership continuity through candidates who can readily fill critical positions. The shared benefits of an effective succession plan are based on a simple idea: by investing in the people that make up your organization, you are investing in the organization's ongoing success.

Rothwell (2010) differentiated replacement planning from succession planning. According to him, replacement is about finding backups to fill vacancies on an organization while succession is about grooming the talent needed for the future. Likewise, he gave insight on the importance of succession planning in the present times. First, many organizations are experiencing the effects of aging workforces. Second, concerns about terrorism have raised the stakes on prudent planning to ensure that leaders and other key workers have backups in case they are needed. Finally, years of downsizing and other cost-cutting measures have reduced the internal bench strength of many organizations so that it is more difficult to find internal replacements. Many organizational leaders are taking steps now to "grow their own talent."

2.1 Foreign Studies

Another study conducted by Caldwell (2007) in a working paper for the UCEDD Network, entitled "Elements of Effective Succession Planning" mentioned that although a number of university leaders have begun to recognize the need to train the next generation of leaders, such programs are typically driven by individuals rather by institutions. Some view that changes in leadership at higher educational institutions are often personal and tribal in nature, and that succession decisions are often controlled by Boards or selection committees outside of the department, who can choose whether to maintain continuity and momentum, or make significant changes to institutional direction and focus. In this regard, succession planning cannot occur in isolation; rather, the elements of successful succession efforts are rooted in four major and interrelated organizational processes: leadership development, transition planning, capturing and

transmitting institutional and technical memory, and transmitting important relationships.

Furthermore, she listed some leadership development strategies for higher education which address many issues that are particular to the academic setting:

- Academics are often ambivalent about assuming leadership roles.
- Professional identity and sense of satisfaction from work of leaders in higher education settings are often derived principally from their professional expertise and accomplishments – not for their leadership potential.
- Those in higher education settings are often not recruited for their leadership potential, but rather are selected and rewarded for their research, course development, and/or teaching skills.
- Often, the institutional system tends to snuff out the spark of enthusiasm for leadership before the flame is ignited.
- The prestige of specific professional disciplines drains off potential leaders into profitable non-leadership roles.
- Many academics are unwilling to give up their professional and personal lives for ones consumed by leadership responsibilities.

Another study made by Richards (2009) entitled “A New Paradigm: Strategies for Succession Planning in Higher Education”, in her paper she presented a comprehensive information and notion of succession planning across both faculty and administrative positions. She mentioned about the need for colleges and universities to develop future leaders who are well positioned and ready to assume leadership posts at colleges and universities across the country. Colleges and universities without deliberate strategies for attracting, developing, and retaining existing or new talent could suffer leadership shortages in the future. It was stated in her study that while formal succession planning is not prevalent in higher education, most colleges and universities are concerned with and are addressing leadership development opportunities for employees.

Likewise, the purpose of the study was to uncover if and how institutions of higher education were currently approaching succession planning and understand if there are specific considerations for planning in the academic culture; cultures traditionally driven by non-profit missions, collegial cultures and shared-governance. As such, the goals of the study were 3-fold. First, it sought to understand if institutions had formal succession plans and explore whether or not the governance structure impacted decision making and approaches to succession planning. Second, if organizational culture influenced an institution’s approach to succession planning. Finally, to uncover potential strategies, methods, and/or processes that were important to institutions as they thought about developing and retaining leadership talent through formal succession planning. By focusing the research on these goals, the study yielded outcomes in the form of a themes and a series of succession planning strategies that may be helpful to future institutions that seek to implement succession plan efforts.

Gonzales (2010) in her working paper entitled “Leadership, Diversity, and Succession planning in Academia” proposed that the connection between the guild and the corporation be strengthened and become more of a two way street. She further discussed the distinction between two levels of administrators: deans and above who are professional administrators, and department chairs and below, who characterized as casual administrators. People should have dual career ladders and be able to move back and forth between technical and managerial jobs, that is, between the guild and the corporation. Likewise, it was highly underlined that institutions of higher education need to become more sophisticated so that they can recognize good leadership when they see it. To find leaders in places where they are likely to be overlooked by the casual observer can only be done through a deliberate, thoughtful and sustained process of succession planning.

Another similar study on succession planning is the research paper of Coward (2012) entitled “A Quantitative Study: Administrative Leaders’ Perceptions of Succession Planning and Management Practices within Community Colleges. The study delved into the perceptions of senior administrative and middle manager community college leaders regarding current succession planning and management practices occurring within their institutions. A suitable succession planning and management instrument was not found; therefore, the Wright-Coward Succession Planning and Management Survey (WCSPMS) instrument was developed. An exploratory factor analysis was used to address research question one and test the structural relationship of the common succession planning and management components of the survey. A second statistical procedure, multivariate analysis of variance, was used to analyze differences between the four dependent measures of succession planning and management and leadership level, and institutional factors. Findings from this study suggested (1) items on the WCSPMS instrument are correlated and three relatively independent succession planning and management factors are associated with the 20 underlying items, and (2) there is a statistical significant difference between leadership level as regards to perceptions of succession planning and management practices. Furthermore, this study indicated there is much work to be done by community college leaders in the area of succession planning and management.

III. Research Methodology

This chapter presents the research methodology, population and sample size, description of respondents, instrumentation, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment employed and used by the researcher.

3. Research Method Used

The researcher made use of descriptive-evaluative method. This is a research method that focuses on present condition with a purpose of discovering new truth such as

increased extent of knowledge, new generalization, an increased insight into factors that are operating, discovery of new causal-relationship, or more accurate formulation of the problem to be solved. Specifically, descriptive-evaluative is a design that will appraise carefully the worthiness of the current study (Zulueta and Costales Jr., 2005). In this study, the researcher sought to determine the level of awareness in succession planning and management practices of educational leaders and academic staff of Gulf College.

3.1 Population and Sampling Frame

The researchers gathered the data for this study from the school leaders and academic staff of Gulf College in the Sultanate of Oman.

3.2 Description of the Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Deputy Deans, Head of Faculty, Program Leaders, Centre Managers, Coordinators and lecturers from Gulf College, a private institution in the Sultanate of Oman.

3.3 Statistical Treatment

Statistical procedures were used to analyze the quantitative data. The information gathered was collated and interpreted using SPSS. Hence, the data obtained were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Specifically, the following statistical formulae were used to analyze the collected data:

A. Frequency and Percentage Distributions were used to classify the respondents according to personal profiles such as age, academic position and educational attainment; the frequency also presented the actual response of the respondents to a specific question or item in the questionnaires.

The percentage of the item is computed by dividing it with the sample total number of respondents. The formula used in the application of this technique is:

$$\% = \frac{F}{N} * 100$$

where:

% = percentage

F = frequency

N = number of cases or total sample

B. Weighted Mean - this was used to compute the average of responses of the respondents on their awareness on succession planning and management practices.

C. Computed r – this was used to measure the strength of correlation of the respondents' profile and their awareness on succession planning and management practices.

IV. Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

In this chapter, the data is presented in tabular form, its contents analyzed and interpreted based on the instituted information. This study aimed to determine the level of awareness in succession planning and management practices of educational leaders and academic staff of Gulf College. The order of presentation was based on the research problem.

A. What is the profile of the respondents based on the following personal variables?

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Age

Age	F	%
30 Years Old Below	3	7.9
31-40 Years Old	11	28.9
41-50 Years Old	17	44.7
51-60 Years Old	7	18.4
More Than 60 Years Old	0	0
No Response	0	0
Total Population	38	100

Table 1 shows the age of the respondents. There are three (3) or 7.9 percent from 30 years old and below; eleven (11) or 28.9 percent from 31-40 years old; seventeen (17) or 44.7 percent from 41-50 years old and seven (7) or 18.4 percent from 51-60 years old. Majority of the respondents are within 41-50 years old. On an experiential level, this result may be attributed to the fact that most administrators thrive in their career in this age range.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	F	%
Bachelor	2	5.3
M.A.	15	39.5
PhD/EdD	21	55.3
No Response	0	0
Total Population	38	100

Table 2 shows the educational attainment of the respondents. There are two (2) or 5.3 percent Bachelor, fifteen (15) or 39.5 percent M.A and twenty one (21) or 55.3 percent PhD/EdD. Majority of the respondents are PhD holders.

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Academic Position

Academic Position	F	%
Deputy Dean	1	2.6
Head of Faculty	2	5.3
Centre Manager	5	13.2

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Program Leader	6	15.8
Coordinator	6	15.8
Lecturer	18	47.4
Total Population	38	100

Table 3 shows the academic positions of the respondents. There is only one (1) or 2.6 percent for Deputy Dean; two (2) or 5.3 percent Head of Faculty; five (5) or 13.2 percent Centre Manager; six (6) or 15.8 percent Program leader and Coordinator respectively; eighteen (18) or 47.4 percent lecturer. Most of the respondents are lecturers.

Similarly, Gonzalez (2010) makes a distinction between two levels of academic administrators: deans and above are (professional administrators) and department chairs and below are (casual administrators). Since all faculty members engage in managerial activities as directors of academic programs, principal investigators of grants, committee members or chairs. She proposes that the connection between the guild and the corporation be strengthened and become more of a two-way street.

B. What is the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of the respondents in terms of:

Table 4: Level of Awareness of Succession Planning and Management Practices of the Respondents

Components	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level	Description
Communicate Expectations	1.00	4.80	2.8211	.82500	Moderate	Aware
Organization Assessment and Alignment	1.00	4.80	2.6737	.89130	Moderate	Aware
Talent & Training Development	1.00	4.80	2.3789	.89900	Low	Less Aware
Process Evaluation	1.20	4.80	2.5211	.87183	Low	Less Aware

Table 4 presents the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices of the respondents. In terms of communicate expectations and organization assessment and alignment, the level of awareness of the respondents is moderate with a verbal description of aware. However, for talent and training development, the level of awareness is low with a verbal description of less aware.

It can be inferred from the result that the respondents are aware of the succession planning and management practices on two components, communicate expectations and organization assessment and alignment.

The result under this area gives an impression that respondents are aware of the succession planning and practices, however, the programs on succession planning are not properly allotted to implement organization and assessment. Likewise, it can be inferred from the data, that there is a need to enhance training and development programs for all the members of the institution. The institution's leadership may demonstrate support of the training and development of employees by creating mentor

and leadership training programs, by utilizing individual employee development plans, and by identifying and/or developing a qualified pool of talent.

C. Is there a significant relationship between the level of succession planning and management practices and the respondents' profile?

Table 5: Significant Relationship between Succession Planning and Management Practices and the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Age

Respondents' Profile	Dependent variable	Type III Sum of Sq	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Square	Decision
Age	Communicate Expectations	3.436	3	1.145	1.611	.239	.287	Accept
	Organization Assessment and Alignment	5.100	3	1.700	2.327	.126	.368	Accept
	Talent Training and Development	7.534	3	2.511	4.247	.029	.515	Reject
	Process Evaluation	7.852	3	2.617	3.706	.043	.481	Reject

Table 5 reveals the significant relationship between succession planning and management practices and the respondents' profile according to age.

It can be gleaned from the results that age has a significant relationship in two components of succession planning and management practices which are talent training and development and process evaluation as shown in the table. Thus, when talent training and development and process evaluation were plotted against age, computed *r* was computed as 0.29 and 0.43 respectively. Likewise, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between succession planning and management practices and age. This particular result gives an impression that age is an important aspect of determining the level of awareness of succession planning and management practices among educational leaders.

Table 6: Significant Relationship between Succession Planning and Management Practices and the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Respondents' Profile	Components	Type III Sum of Sq	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Square	Decision
Educational attainment	Communicate Expectations	.301	2	.151	.212	.812	.034	Accept
	Organization Assessment and Alignment	.995	2	.498	.681	.525	.102	Accept
	Talent and Training Development	.959	2	.480	.811	.467	.119	Accept
	Process Evaluation	1.176	2	.588	.833	.459	.122	Accept

Table 6 discloses the significant relationship between succession planning and management practices and the respondents' profile according to educational attainment. The results show that when succession planning and management practices were plotted against educational attainment, the computed r is higher than 0.05 thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between overall succession planning and management practices and educational attainment.

Table 7: Significant Relationship between Succession Planning and Management Practices and the Respondents' Profile When Grouped According to Academic Positions

Respondents' Profile	Dependent variable	Type III Sum of Sq	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Square	Decision
Academic Position	Communicate Expectations	1.675	5	.335	.471	.791	.164	Accept
	Organisation Assessment and Alignment	3.293	5	.659	.902	.511	.273	Accept
	Talent Training and Development	1.972	5	.394	.667	.656	.217	Accept
	Process Evaluation	.921	5	.184	.261	.926	.098	Accept

Table 7 discloses the significant relationship between succession planning and management practices and the respondents' profile according to academic positions. The results show that when succession planning and management practices were plotted against academic positions, the computed r is higher than 0.05 thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between overall succession planning and management practices and educational attainment.

5. Conclusions

1. In terms of *talent training and development and process evaluation* as against the respondents' profile, the result showed that only the respondents' age has a significant relationship in terms of succession planning and management practices.
2. The level of awareness of the respondents as regards to succession planning and management practices in terms of *communicate expectations and organization assessment and alignment* must be strengthened, since they have a verbal interpretation of aware. Wright Coward indicates in her instrument that awareness does not mean involvement. Indeed, educational leaders may be aware of the succession planning and practices in their institutions but no involvement in actual succession planning.

3. The level of awareness of the respondents as regards to succession planning and management practices in terms of *talent training and development as well as process evaluation* have marked less aware, this implies that although educational leaders have some knowledge in succession planning and management practices, their involvement is limited. Hence, implementation is not actualized.

5.1 Recommendations

1. Educational leaders, particularly the top and middle managers should provide an open avenue in succession planning and practices specifically in communicate expectations, organization and assessment, talent and training development programs, and process evaluation.
2. Educational leaders must provide programs and plans to develop internal successors who will take the lead to remain competitive in the future. An apprenticeship programs must be provided for incoming educational leaders or managers.
3. Since, this research is a trail blazer in succession planning and management practices, further research must be conducted including other intervening variables and covering other colleges and universities, is highly recommended.

References

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